

Recommendations for Finite Element Modelling of Nickel-Titanium Stents – Verification and Validation Activities

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Highlights

- Application of relevant verification and validation activities to address the credibility of a FE model for self-expanding nickel-titanium stent, as per ASME VV-40 standard.
- Verification activities in three common contexts of use (radial compression, deployment in a vessel, and fatigue estimation), and quantification of numerical discretization on relevant quantities of interests for each context.
- Sensitivity to model inputs as stent strut dimensions and to nickel-titanium material parameters.
- Validation with *in vitro* experiments for deployment in a vessel, considering idealized and realistic vessel geometries and comparison of clinically relevant parameters.

35 **ABSTRACT**

36 *Background* – The objective of this study is to present a credibility assessment of finite element
37 modelling of self-expanding Ni-Ti stents through verification and validation (VV) activities, as set out
38 in the ASME VV-40 standard. As part of the study, the role of calculation verification, model input
39 sensitivity, and model validation is examined across three different application contexts (radial
40 compression, stent deployment in a vessel, fatigue estimation).

41 *Methods* – A commercially available self-expanding nickel-titanium stent was modelled, and
42 calculation verification activities addressed the effects of mesh density, element integration and
43 stable time increment on different quantities of interests, for each context of use considered.
44 Sensitivity analysis of the geometrical and material input parameters and validation of deployment
45 configuration with *in vitro* comparators were investigated.

46 *Results* – Global and local outputs were sensitive to the mesh discretisation, with substantial variability
47 evident when the mesh density was less than 4×4 elements across the strut cross-section. Element
48 formulation also led to substantial variation depending on the chosen integration options.
49 Furthermore, for explicit analyses, model results were highly sensitive to the chosen target time
50 increment (e.g., mass scaling parameters), irrespective of whether the ratios of kinetic and internal
51 energies were kept below 5%. It was found that fatigue life simulation was the most sensitive context
52 of use considered, with the estimation of fatigue safety factor (*FSF*) varying by almost an order of
53 magnitude depending on the selection of discretization parameters. In terms of model inputs, the
54 predictions of outputs such as radial force and stresses, showed relatively low sensitivity to Ni-Ti
55 material parameters, which suggests that the calibration approaches used in the literature to date
56 appear reasonable, but a higher sensitivity to stent geometry (namely strut thickness and width). In
57 contrast, the prediction of vessel diameter following deployment was least sensitive to numerical
58 parameters, and small errors ($\sim 1\text{-}2\%$) were found among the model and *in vitro* comparators in the
59 prediction of diameter and lumen area post-deployment.

60 *Conclusion* – To increase the credibility of finite element models of Ni-Ti stents, our verification
61 analysis indicates that 4×4 element density across the strut width and thickness is required for
62 prediction of radial compression/deployment, while a 6×6 element density or finer is necessary for
63 reliable estimates of fatigue life. Reduced integration over full integration continuum hexahedral
64 elements should be preferred to avoid overly stiff behaviour in bending. For explicit analysis, model
65 sensitivity to mass scaling or time incrementation parameters should be investigated independently,
66 irrespective of whether the ratios of kinetic and internal energies are below 5%. Model input
67 sensitivity analysis highlighted the importance of capturing the geometric dimensions of the stent, in
68 particular the strut width, while model results are less sensitive to Ni-Ti material parameters,
69 suggesting that device-level calibration of material behaviour are reasonable. Finally, the validation of
70 stent deployment through the use of *in vitro* mock vessels offers a simple and accurate validation
71 method when predicting lumen gain, and lumen area, provided that the material of the vessel is
72 appropriately characterized and modelled.

73

74 **1 Introduction**

75 Self-expanding nickel-titanium (Ni-Ti) stents have become the gold-standard of treatment across a
76 range of vascular indications ¹⁻⁵, due to the shape memory and superelastic properties of the metal
77 alloy. In the certification process for these endovascular devices, manufacturers must provide a
78 substantial body of pre-clinical evidence that demonstrates suitable mechanical performance of the
79 stent and delivery system, which is described in detail by the ISO 25539 ⁶ standard. While the vast
80 majority of these certification activities currently involve physical testing, the Food and Drug
81 Administration (FDA) has for many years advocated the use of computer modelling in the regulatory
82 evaluation of devices ⁷. Finite element analysis is already one of the requirements in the certification
83 of endovascular stents for fatigue and durability ⁶, and general recommendations and considerations
84 for its use in radial compression analysis are described by ASTM-F2514 ⁸. A recent report by their
85 Senior Science Council highlights the clear ambition from the FDA to increase the role of modelling
86 and simulation in the regulatory process ^{7,9}. On the other hand, there is currently no technical standard
87 harmonised in the EU regulatory system to demonstrate the credibility of an *in silico trial* solution ¹⁰.
88 For many years, a key concern around the increasing use of computational modelling in the medical
89 device sector was the lack of clear guidance on how to assess the model credibility, namely its ability
90 to replicate the modelled reality within a predefined tolerance. In 2018, the American Society of
91 Mechanical Engineers (ASME) released the VV-40 “Verification and Validation in Computational
92 Modeling of Medical Devices” ¹¹, which establishes a risk-informed credibility assessment framework
93 based on verification, validation and uncertainty quantification activities. The ASME VV-40 standard
94 outlines a framework that begins with the definition of the question of interest (QOI), a specific
95 question being addressed with a computational model, and a context of use (COU), which specifies
96 the role of modelling and simulation in addressing the QOI. It also defines a method to quantify the
97 model risk, that is the possibility that the model may lead to a false/incorrect conclusion about device
98 performance resulting in adverse outcomes. Verification and validation are common concepts used to

99 describe the procedure for assessing that a product, service or system meets requirements and
100 specifications defined for its intended purpose ¹². The verification procedure evaluates whether the
101 product, service or system conforms to its specifications. The validation procedure ensures that the
102 product, service or system complies with the requirements or expectations of current and potential
103 stakeholders (e.g., customers). In the context computational models and the ASME VV-40 standard,
104 these concepts assume a specific meaning, whereby verification ensures a computational model is
105 correctly implemented with respect of the conceptual model (e.g., it matches the specifications and
106 assumptions for the given purpose of its application). On the other hand, validation assesses the
107 accuracy of the model in representing the real system, consistently with the intended application of
108 the model. While the ASME VV-40 standard now represents one of the pillars of regulatory reference
109 to determine model credibility in the regulatory decision-making process, there are limited examples
110 of its effective application of the VV-40 framework to Ni-Ti-based vascular devices, despite extensive
111 research on these implants.

112 The objective of this study is to present a credibility assessment of finite element modelling of self-
113 expanding Ni-Ti stents through verification and validation activities, as set out in the ASME VV-40
114 standard. In this paper, we first provide a review of recent computational studies that predict the
115 mechanical performance of self-expanding Ni-Ti stents. Based on this, we conducted a range of VV
116 activities for several commonly investigated COUs for Ni-Ti devices. These COUs included simulated
117 mechanical bench tests, device deployment in idealised and realistic vessels and fatigue-behaviour
118 assessment. Within the verification activities, we identified the key model sensitivities for each COU
119 relating to pertinent issues, such as spatial and temporal discretization, and element formulation.
120 Within the validation activities, we performed a sensitivity analysis to model inputs, namely
121 geometrical and material parameters in radial compression modelling. Finally, we used *in vitro*
122 comparators for assessing the configuration after the deployment in a vessel.

123 2 Review of Computational Modelling of Nickel-Titanium Endovascular

124 Devices

125 Computational modelling has been used to predict a range of mechanical characteristics of
126 endovascular Ni-Ti-based devices, from *in silico* bench testing to assess functional mechanical
127 performance¹³, predictions of fatigue behaviour¹⁴ and deployment in patient-specific geometries^{15,16}.
128 While the methodologies followed appear to be well-established and generally aligned with guidance
129 in commercial software manuals¹⁷, few studies have presented a detailed verification and validation
130 of their modelling frameworks. Error! Reference source not found. presents a summary of recent
131 computational studies that have simulated the performance of Ni-Ti-based devices. It includes details
132 of the model framework, solver settings, model discretisation, input and output data, and verification
133 and validation activities. This summary highlights similarities and inconsistencies in the modelling
134 approaches used, which are in some cases not even fully described, despite the published guidelines
135 on reporting of computational models being now available¹⁸.

136 Given the significant nonlinearities that are encountered due to the presence of large deformations
137 and complex interactions, the use of explicit solver^{13,15,16,19–23} is preferred over implicit approaches^{24–}
138²⁶ when modelling Ni-Ti devices^{27,28}. However, explicit solution schemes are not conditionally stable,
139 and many studies have applied generic criteria to ensure quasi-static conditions, which require the
140 ratio of kinetic energy to internal energy to be kept below 5%^{16,21,29}, with additional numerical
141 damping added if required²². The stable time increment is not always reported in models of this type,
142 with examples ranging from 4E-06 s to 1E-08 s^{16,23}, with these values depending greatly on the
143 boundary conditions and loading rate in use. While a minimum density of 4 × 4 hexahedral elements
144 across the stent-strut (e.g., width × thickness) has been suggested^{17,19,29} with linear reduced
145 integration^{15,16,23,29}, the details of mesh density and element type details are sometimes not stated
146^{20,30} or have been selected based on previous literature²³, with the procedure and outcomes of the
147 verification activities rarely made available^{21,31,32}. Also, there is substantial variation in how both

148 geometric and material model inputs are derived. In some cases, the geometry of the device is
149 obtained directly from the manufacturer^{21,22}. As this information can be commercially sensitive, many
150 authors have been forced to reconstruct the geometry through imaging techniques such as optical
151 microscopy or micro-computer tomography (micro-CT)^{13-15,19}, which might add substantial
152 uncertainty. To model the superelastic behaviour of Ni-Ti, the constitutive law from Auricchio and
153 Taylor³³ is universally used^{14,15,34-38,16,19-24,29}, with this model now available as a built-in option in
154 several commercial software packages such as Abaqus²⁹, ANSYS³⁹ and COMSOL Multiphysics⁴⁰.
155 However, this constitutive model presents challenges as it requires up to 15 independent parameters
156 to be determined⁴¹. In some studies, these have been derived from uniaxial tensile testing of dog-
157 bone specimens¹⁴, tube sections²⁰, wires/multi-wire specimens²¹, or have been provided directly by
158 the manufacturer^{16,22}. In many other studies, these parameters have been calibrated directly to the
159 device response or have been obtained from literature^{15,19,34,35}, which in some cases uses source data
160 from devices with distinctly different designs and applications. Together, these verification aspects
161 lead to several issues that create uncertainty around the model set-up that requires careful
162 consideration and highlight the need for robust validation efforts for individual models.

163 Validation is generally addressed by comparing the computational model with a comparator, which
164 could be animals, cadavers, patients, *in vitro* specimens or phantoms. When the model is developed
165 to guide decisions during the design phase of the device, common validation strategies make use of
166 *in vitro* mechanical bench tests, such as radial compression, axial tension, and bending. For example,
167 McKenna et al.^{13,29} developed a FE model of braided and laser-cut self-expanding Ni-Ti stents, which
168 was compared against experiments through quantitative (e.g., radial and axial tests) and qualitative
169 (e.g., bending configurations) data and applied the model to predict mechanical behaviour on
170 alternative stent designs and polymer covers. However, when models are developed to address the
171 clinical performance of a device, further validation activities are required to ensure that interactions
172 with a vessel are correctly accounted for. With this in mind, Bernini et al.⁴² calibrated stent material
173 parameters through the device radial response and subsequently validated the model performance

174 with an *in vitro* comparator of deployment in a straight silicone vessel. A similar approach was
175 previously developed by Berti et al.⁴³, although for a FE model of a platinum-chromium stent for
176 coronary applications. Here, the model was validated against *in vitro* experiments of deployment in
177 idealised straight and bifurcated vessels, and in more realistic patient-specific anatomies obtained
178 using 3D-printing technology. The authors suggested several relevant parameters to use in the
179 comparison, which included outer diameter gain and stent malapposition, and emphasised the
180 importance of mechanical characterisation of the vessel material to ensure that the radial response
181 was in a physiologically relevant range. While this is an excellent example of model validation carried
182 out for coronary devices, the application of the VV-40 standard to self-expanding Ni-Ti-based devices
183 is limited, despite their widespread use.

184 In the context of VV-40, only a few studies have clearly addressed aspects of verification and validation
185 for Ni-Ti cardiovascular devices. Luraghi et al.^{22,31} applied the ASME VV-40 standard to address the
186 capability of a FE model of a stent-retriever device with the objective of predicting revascularization
187 outcomes in realistic scenarios. Verification activities were carried out to support the choice of
188 suitable element discretization and formulation, and validation was achieved through *in vitro*
189 thrombectomy tests in idealized funnel- and U-shaped tubes, and more realistic patient-specific
190 vessels. Zaccaria et al.²¹ adopted the ASME VV-40 standard to identify the model risk and define a
191 suitable *in vitro* experimental campaign for a Ni-Ti venous system to treat compression disorders. The
192 authors established a framework to perform verification and validation activities applicable to a stent-
193 like device. Verification activities quantified the effects of mesh density and element formulation on
194 local and global parameters, namely stress and force. A comprehensive report on the method used to
195 derive geometrical and material parameters was also included in the appendix and model validation
196 was addressed within the context of device delivery (e.g., assembly, retraction and deployment in a
197 realistic vessel) by comparing among *in silico* and *in vitro* outcomes. Beyond these examples, the vast
198 majority of other computational studies do not include any form of independent validation of their
199 model prediction. Despite this, computational models of Ni-Ti stents have been widely used to predict

200 the performance of stents in complex scenarios, including implantation behaviour in patient-specific
 201 vessels ^{15,16} and fatigue performance. However, the predictive power of these models remains
 202 questionable without rigorous assessment of model credibility through appropriate verification and
 203 validation activities.

204 3 Materials and Methods

205 3.1 ASME VV-40 Standard

206 The ASME VV-40 standard provides a risk-informed credibility assessment framework through
 207 verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification activities for computational modelling in the
 208 medical device industry. The VV-40 document describes a pathway that encompasses the following
 209 steps: (i) definition of the question of interest (QOI), which will be addressed by the computational
 210 model; (ii) the definition of the context of use (COU), which states the scope and role of the
 211 computational model in addressing the QOI; (iii) assessment of the model risk within the COU and the
 212 potential effects of adverse outcomes as a consequence of an incorrect decision driven by the model;
 213 (iv) establishment of credibility goal and rigour required for the verification, validation, and
 214 applicability activities such that the model credibility is commensurate with the model risk ⁴⁴, as
 215 summarized in **Table 1**.

216 *Table 1: ASME VV-40 standard process flow.*

Process Step	Process Component	Credibility Factors
Verification	Code	Numerical code verification Software quality assurance
	Calculation	Discretization error Numerical solver error Use error
Validation	Model	Model Form Model Inputs
	Comparator	Test Samples Test Conditions
	Assessment	Equivalency of Input parameters Output Comparison

Applicability	Relevance of the quantities of interest Relevance of the validation activities to the context of use
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218 3.2 Study Design

219 In this study, the credibility of FE modelling of a self-expanding Ni-Ti stent was addressed through
220 conventional scenarios where structural analysis is employed for such devices (examples in Error!
221 Reference source not found.). Common applications of FE models of Ni-Ti stents could be classified as
222 (i) modelling of standard mechanical bench tests (e.g. axial tension/compression and radial
223 compression test^{21,29}), (ii) predictions of deployment either in an idealised straight vessel or in patient-
224 specific realistic anatomies^{15,16}, and (iii) predictions of fatigue behaviour¹⁴. These applications were
225 classified in three COUs and relevant VV activities were selected accordingly¹⁷:

- 226 ▪ *COU-1: Radial compression* is often used for deriving the material parameters for Ni-Ti^{45,46} or
227 evaluating the functional performance of different stent designs through relevant mechanical
228 parameters (e.g., radial strength, radial resistive force, chronic outward force, stress field
229 induced in the device)²⁹, as advised in the ASTM F3067 standard⁴⁷. For COU-1, calculation
230 verification was carried out by examining mesh discretization, temporal discretization, and
231 element integration selection, while validation of the model inputs was performed through a
232 detailed sensitivity analysis on both geometric and material model parameters.
- 233 ▪ *COU-2: Stent deployment* predictions in vessel-like geometries are often used to establish
234 device performance in restoring vessel patency, or assess the level of stress induced in the
235 device or/and in the vessel tissue^{16,48}. For COU-2, calculation verification was carried out for
236 mesh discretization, temporal discretization, and element formulation selection, while
237 validation of the computational model was investigated through *in vitro* comparators.
- 238 ▪ *COU-3: Fatigue predictions* from pulsatile loading of the device are commonly carried out to
239 mimic ASTM F2477⁴⁹ conditions. Simulations generally compute the mean (ϵ_m) and

240 alternating strain (ϵ_a) components and evaluate the fatigue safety factor (FSF) to estimate
 241 lifetime of the device ⁵⁰. For COU-3, calculation verification was carried out for mesh
 242 discretization, temporal discretization, and element formulation selection to assess their
 243 effects on the prediction of ϵ_m and ϵ_a for the plotting of the constant life diagrams and on the
 244 FSF .

245 **Table 2** provides a summary of the COUs under study, with details of the verification and validation
 246 activities performed.

247 **Table 2.** Definition of the COUs and the related verification and validation activities addressed within this study.

	COU-1	COU-2	COU-3
Context Of Use	Predict the mechanical performance of the stent subjected to a radial compression test.	Predict the configuration of a stent when deployed in a vessel, considering idealized and realistic geometries.	Predict the fatigue performance of the device when subjected to radial pulsatile pressure.
Quantity of Interest (QoI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Radial force - diameter curve and derived parameters such as maximum force at crimp (F_{max}) and chronic outward force (COF). ▪ Stress distribution on the peak of the strut. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Vessel outer/inner diameter (OD/ID). ▪ Minimum lumen area (MLA) ▪ Incomplete strut apposition (ISA). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mean and alternating strain components. ▪ Fatigue safety factor (FSF).
Verification Activities	Aspects of calculation verification: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ mesh density; ▪ element integration; ▪ stable time increment. 	Aspects of calculation verification: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ mesh density; ▪ element integration; ▪ stable time increment. 	Aspects of calculation verification: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ mesh density; ▪ element integration; ▪ stable time increment.
Validation Activities	Sensitivity analysis on model inputs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ geometry (strut thickness and width) considering a $\pm 10\%$ variation; ▪ nickel-titanium material parameters considering a $\pm 10\%$ variation. 	Comparison with <i>in vitro</i> configuration of deployment: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ straight vessels made of silicone; ▪ 3D-printed patient-specific vessels made of resin. 	Not addressed.

248 3.3 General Description of the FE Model

249 3.3.1 Stent Device and Functional Unit

250 The Zilver PTX (Cook Medical, USA) is a self-expanding Ni-Ti stent intended for the treatment of
 251 restenotic symptomatic lesions in the iliac artery, superficial femoral artery and in the above-the-knee
 252 femoropopliteal artery. The device is composed of sequential rings that feature open-cell Z-shaped

253 struts with a peak-to-valley design and it is produced in a variable range of nominal diameter (6.0 -
254 10.0 mm) and length (20.0 - 200.0 mm) ⁵¹.

255 A 3D model of the device was created with Inventor® 2018 software (Autodesk, San Rafael, CA, United
256 States) based on measurements from optical microscopy and micro-CT imaging. Similar to most stent
257 designs, the Zilver PTX has a repeating pattern (**Figure 1a**) that allows a functional unit of the 6.0 × 60
258 mm device to be used to reduce the system size, with axisymmetric boundary conditions applied at
259 the truncated edges (**Figure 1c**). This is a common approach for stent modelling where geometry,
260 loading and boundary conditions possess symmetry ⁵². The functional unit model was used for running
261 verification activities to investigate the effects of discretization error, and for running the sensitivity
262 analysis over model inputs. Otherwise, the full geometry of the stent was considered when validating
263 against the *in vitro* mock vessel comparators, as it is more representative of the stent-to-lumen
264 interaction along the whole length of the device. A stent with a length of 60.0 mm was modelled in
265 varying diameter sizes (6.0, 7.0 and 9.0 mm) to match the devices available for the experimental
266 campaign.

267 The complex nonlinear behaviour of Ni-Ti (**Figure 1d**) was implemented through the built-in VUMAT
268 material formulation by Auricchio and Taylor ⁵³ available in Abaqus, where the values for material
269 parameters were determined from experimental tests in a previous work ⁴².

270

271 **Figure 1.** Stent model: (a) 2D sketch of the stent with detail of the functional unit used in the verification step; (b) comparison
 272 of crimped and expanded configurations; (c) functional unit; (d) superelastic Ni-Ti constitutive law; (e) details of width (w_s)
 273 and thickness (t_s) strut dimensions.

274 3.3.2 Simulation Strategy and Settings

275 The FE model included non-linearity from the superelastic material constitutive law of Ni-Ti⁵³, the
 276 complex contact interactions and large deformations occurring in the analysis. The Abaqus/Explicit
 277 solver was used to solve the dynamic equations of equilibrium⁵², whose general form for a non-linear
 278 explicit analysis is written as:

$$[M]\{\ddot{\mathbf{u}}\} + [C]\{\dot{\mathbf{u}}\} + [K]\{\mathbf{u}\} = \{\mathbf{F}(t)\} \quad (3.1)$$

279 where $\{\mathbf{F}(t)\}$ is the time-dependent load vector; $[M]$, $[C]$ and $[K]$ are the global mass, damping and
 280 stiffness matrices; $\{\ddot{\mathbf{u}}\}$, $\{\dot{\mathbf{u}}\}$, $\{\mathbf{u}\}$ are the nodal acceleration, velocity and displacement vectors,
 281 respectively^{28,54}.

282 The steps implemented for the simulation of each COU are outlined here.

283 COU-1: A radial pattern of rigid plates was used to enforce compression of the device from a diameter
 284 of 6.00 mm to 2.4 mm within a time step of 4 s (**Figure 2**, Step 1). The displacement was then released
 285 within a time step of 4 s and to allow the stent to recover freely (**Figure 2**, Step 2). Interactions
 286 between the stent surface and the plates was active, as well as self-contact among the stent surface.
 287 For COU-1, a global and a local output were compared, as suggested in literature⁵⁵, namely the radial

288 force-diameter curve and the trend of maximum principal stress at the internal edge of the V peak
289 (**Figure 3b**).

290 COU-2: For implantation within a vessel, these models followed the identical process outlined for COU-
291 1, whereby the stent was crimped from a diameter of 6.0 mm to 2.4 mm (**Figure 2**, Step 1) followed
292 by release in the same timeframe. However, during the release step in COU-2, the interaction between
293 the inner lumen of the vessel and the device was active to allow for deployment in both straight and
294 patient-specific geometries (**Figure 2**, Step 2). For deployment in more realistic anatomical vessel an
295 additional morphing procedure is required, as described in a previous paper⁴². For COU-2, clinically
296 relevant parameters such as the outer vessel diameter, minimum lumen area, and incomplete stent
297 apposition were measured (**Figure 5d**).

298 COU-3: Following the implantation procedure described above, COU-3 included an additional time
299 step to apply a pulsatile load to evaluate the fatigue behaviour. Three cycles of blood pressure
300 oscillating between the diastolic and the systolic values of 80 mmHg and 120 mmHg with a frequency
301 of 1.2 Hz, corresponding to the average blood pulsation conditions were applied²³ (**Figure 2**, Step 3).
302 A strain-based criterion was chosen for the analysis of fatigue given the nature of Ni-Ti alloy
303 constitutive law¹⁴. The alternating (ϵ_a) and mean strain (ϵ_m) components were computed with the
304 scalar method⁵⁶, which was deemed suitable⁸ for the type of loading conditions investigated:

$$\epsilon_m = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{systole}} + \epsilon_{\text{diastole}}}{2} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\epsilon_a = \frac{|\epsilon_{\text{systole}} - \epsilon_{\text{diastole}}|}{2} \quad (3.3)$$

305 The values of these components allowed to plot the constant-life diagram and the alternating strain
306 were used to compute the fatigue safety factor (*FSF*) against the limit value for 10^7 cycles $\epsilon_a^* = 0.4\%$ ⁵⁷,
307 as follows:

$$FSF = \frac{\epsilon_a^*}{\epsilon_a} \quad (3.4)$$

308 During all the steps, the general contact algorithm with a hard contact definition and a friction
 309 coefficient of $\mu = 0.2$ was used, consistent with studies found in literature^{13,15,58}.

310

311 **Figure 2.** Description of the steps for the simulations. **Step 1** includes the crimping of the sub-unit, which is either allowed a
 312 free release (COU-1) or deployed in contact with the vessel (COU-2) in **Step 2**. Finally, the deployed configuration is used to
 313 apply pulsatile blood conditions in **Step 3** for fatigue analysis (COU-3).

314 **3.4 Verification Activities**

315 Most of the studies available in the literature rely on commercial software whose code verification is
316 extensively documented by their developer^{59,60}. Therefore, the verification activities we have focused
317 on here are related to the calculation verification, where we specifically address aspects related to the
318 spatial and temporal refinement¹⁸ of the system, as follows:

- 319 ▪ Mesh density (*MD*): to quantify the error associated with spatial discretization and mesh
320 quality.
- 321 ▪ Element integration (*EI*): to address the influence of different mathematical formulations in
322 the derivation needed to deduce the displacements of finite elements⁶¹.
- 323 ▪ Target time increment (*TTI*): to determine the acceptable stable time increment in the
324 dynamic simulation.

325 **3.4.1 Mesh Density**

326 Four different mesh refinements with a density of elements in the width and thickness of the strut of
327 3×3 , 4×4 , 6×6 , and 8×8 elements (**Figure 3**) were selected. Details regarding the number of
328 elements and nodes, characteristic length and aspect ratio are reported in **Table 3**.

329

330
331

Figure 3. Mesh density: (a) uniform mesh of the functional stent unit; (b) details of the portion selected for the local QoI; (c) comparison of four different element densities.

332

Table 3. Characteristics of mesh grids.

Mesh Grid	3 × 3	4 × 4	6 × 6	8 × 8
Number of elements	2,391	8,404	25,818	62,136
Number of nodes	4,348	13,495	35,910	79,929
Element characteristic length, mm	6.6E-02	4.90E-02	3.3E-02	2.5E-02
Average aspect ratio, -	2.14	1.85	1.80	1.82

333 3.4.2 Element Integration

334 Three-dimensional linear solid elements were used, whose formulation is available with full or
 335 reduced integration options. Within the reduced formulation, the kinematic split is selected as
 336 *average* (default), while *orthogonal* and *centroid* are proposed as alternatives to decrease the
 337 computational costs. The enhanced hourglass control option was added and compared. The 4 × 4
 338 mesh grid was used and details of all the simulation runs are reported in **Table 4**.

339

Table 4. Characteristics of element integration.

Element Integration	Code	Label	Description
Full integration	C3D8	Full	8 Gauss points to integrate the polynomial terms in an element's stiffness matrix.
Reduced integration	C3D8R		1 point to integrate the polynomial terms in an element's stiffness matrix. Different options arise with the choice of kinematic split:
		Red-A	average: based on the uniform strain operator

	Red-AH	average + enhanced hourglass control
	Red-O	orthogonal: based on the centroidal strain operator and a slight modification to the hourglass shape vector
	Red-C	centroid: the centroidal strain operator and the hourglass base vectors

340 3.4.3 Time Step

341 The Abaqus/Explicit solver was chosen for the analysis due to the complex nonlinear contact
342 conditions in the deployment simulation ⁴². The explicit method is conditionally stable since there
343 exists a critical time step Δt_{\min} that must not be exceeded in the analysis and depends on the highest
344 eigenvalue (ω_{\max}) in the model and the fraction of critical damping (ξ) in the highest mode ⁶²:

$$\Delta t_{\min} \leq \frac{2}{\omega_{\max}} \left(\sqrt{1 + \xi^2} - \xi \right) \quad (3.5)$$

345 The explicit procedure solves the system as a wave propagation problem, moving at a dilatation speed
346 of c_d , which for a linear elastic material with a Poisson's ratio of zero depends on Young's modulus E
347 and the material density ρ :

$$c_d = \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho}} \quad (3.6)$$

348 The magnitude of the critical time step depends on the largest natural frequency of the linearized
349 system, hence on the size of the smallest characteristic element length L^e and the dilatation wave
350 speed c_d . The stability time limit can be estimated by:

$$\Delta t = \frac{L^e}{c_d} \quad (3.7)$$

351 To efficiently model a quasi-static problem where the material behaviour is rate-independent (e.g. no
352 viscous behaviour), the loading rate can be increased and mass scaling applied ^{16,21-23,29,63}. Typically,
353 simulations are understood to be quasi-static by evaluating the ratio between kinetic to internal
354 energy ratio ^{21,23} and ensuring that this ratio is below 5% for the simulation. While this criterion
355 appears widely in the literature, it has rarely been independently assessed. In this study, a fixed mass
356 scaling was applied at the beginning of the step on the stent specified by selecting an element target
357 time increment (TTI) with values of 1.0E-05 s, 5.0E-06 s, 1.0E-06 s, 5.0E-07 s for a total step time of 8

358 s, on the 4×4 mesh grid. Results obtained through the explicit solver for the range of *TTI* were
 359 compared with a simulation run with the dynamic implicit method. The implicit algorithm requires
 360 iterative solutions for each time increment, thereby it ensures accuracy of the solution dictated by the
 361 convergence criterion ⁶⁴. A summary of the analyses for calculation verification activities is reported
 362 in **Table 5**.

363 **Table 5.** Summary of the parameters for the calculation verification study.

Model	Mesh Density [width \times thickness]	Element Integration	Time Increment [s]
<i>MD</i> – 3×3	3×3	Full integration	5.0E-06
<i>MD</i> – 4×4	4×4		
<i>MD</i> – 6×6	6×6		
<i>MD</i> – 8×8	8×8		
<i>EI</i> – Full	4×4	Full integration	5.0E-06
<i>EI</i> – Red-A		Reduced - Average	
<i>EI</i> – Red-O		Reduced - Orthogonal	
<i>EI</i> – Red-C		Reduced - Centroid	
<i>TTI</i> – 1.0E-05	4×4	Full integration	1.0E-05
<i>TTI</i> – 5.0E-06			5.0E-06
<i>TTI</i> – 1.0E-06			1.0E-06
<i>TTI</i> – 5.0E-07			5.0E-07

364

365 **3.5 Validation Activities**

366 The validation activities assessed the degree to which the computational model was able to physically
 367 represent the quantities of interest (QoI) in the intended uses ¹⁸. In this study, we sought to
 368 understand the sensitivity of computational model inputs on the predicted result, while also
 369 comparing predictions directly to an *in vitro* comparator. For all the validation activities presented
 370 here, the optimum model parameters were chosen based on the detailed verification analysis, which
 371 meant that all validation models had a mesh density of 4×4 , a reduced integration element
 372 formulation (Red-A) and a target time increment of 5.0 E-6 s.

373 3.5.1 COU-1 Validation – Model Input Analysis

374 The geometry and the material properties of the stent were considered key parameters for the
375 sensitivity analysis on model inputs. For the sensitivity to geometrical inputs, strut thickness ($t_s = 0.197$
376 mm) and width ($w_s = 0.120$ mm) were considered. These dimensional measurements are often
377 acquired with a variety of imaging techniques^{14,15,19,29,65} and are subject to uncertainties. Even when
378 the geometry is known (e.g., CAD is provided by the stent manufacturer), it typically represents the
379 laser-cut configuration, which could be altered during subsequent electropolishing steps. Similarly, to
380 define the material parameters for Ni-Ti, experiments on material specimens have been carried out,
381 although these might present variability among samples, lots, and suppliers⁶⁶. In other cases, studies
382 have used values from the literature, despite the fact that there is substantial variability in these
383 parameters, depending on the alloy composition and/or processing history^{66,67}. In this study, the
384 geometric thickness and width of the stent (**Figure 1e**) and six material parameters describing the Ni-
385 Ti tensile behaviour (**Table 6**) were considered for the sensitivity analysis. For all parameters, a range
386 of $\pm 10\%$ was applied, as advised in literature⁶⁸.

387 **Table 6.** Nickel-titanium material parameters used as reference in the sensitivity analysis.

Parameter	Symbol	Reference Value
Austenite elasticity, MPa	E_A	47,000
Martensite elasticity, MPa	E_M	20,000
Start of transformation loading stress, MPa	σ_L^S	420
End of transformation loading stress, MPa	σ_L^E	500
Start of transformation unloading stress, MPa	σ_U^S	150
End of transformation unloading stress, MPa	σ_U^E	115

388

389 3.5.2 COU-2 Validation – *In Vitro* Comparator

390 The validation for the COU-2 was performed to assess the deployment configuration of the self-
391 expanding stent. We considered implantation both in a straight vessel to assess the capability of the
392 model in predicting the stent-to-vessel interaction and final outer diameter (*OD*), and in 3D-printed
393 patient-specific geometries to access quantitative data as the minimum lumen area (*MLA*) and the

394 incomplete stent apposition (ISA), as reported in **Figure 5d**. The straight vessels were manufactured
395 from silicone by Dynatek Labs, Inc. (Galena, MO, USA) to ensure consistency with the guidelines of ISO
396 7198 ⁶⁹, while two patient-specific vessel geometries ^{42,70,71} were manufactured using a Form 3 Low
397 Force Stereolithography 3D-printer (Formlabs, Massachusetts, USA).

398 **3.5.2.1 Characterization and Calibration of Mock Vessel Material**

399 For robust validation, vessel material parameters were derived directly from the specimens, whereby
400 the mechanical response of the silicon mock vessel was characterized through hoop tests ($n = 3$), as
401 detailed in a previous study ⁴². In the simulation, silicone was modelled with an isotropic elastic
402 constitutive law with a Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$ and an elastic modulus $E = 0.65$ MPa, with these
403 parameters appropriately capturing the uniaxial tensile test data (**Figure 4a**). Similarly, the Elastic 50A
404 Resin material (Formlabs, Massachusetts, USA), designed for medical models undergoing large
405 deformations ⁷², was used for the 3D-printed patient-specific geometries and was characterized by
406 uniaxial tensile testing of dog-bone specimens ($n = 10$) according to the ASTM D638-14 standard ⁷³. A
407 first-order isotropic hyperelastic Neo-Hookean law with $C_{10} = 0.458$ MPa and $D_1 = 0$, provided the
408 optimal fitting of the experimental curve (**Figure 4b**).

409

410 **Figure 4.** Calibration of materials used for the mock vessels: **(a)** experimental and computational stress-strain curves derived
411 from the hoop tests on silicone material; **(b)** experimental and computational stress-strain curves derived from uniaxial tensile
412 dog-bone specimens of Elastic 50A Resin.

413

414

415 **Figure 5. (a)** Comparison of patient-specific geometries as 3D-printed resin vessels (top) and FE model (bottom); **(b)** sequence
 416 of stent deployment into a resin mock vessel; **(c)** DICOM cross-sectional image (left) and schematics of the performance
 417 indicators.

418 3.5.2.2 Experimental Deployment in Mock Vessels

419 The experimental deployment was performed in a water bath at a temperature of 37°C to ensure
 420 devices were in the appropriate superelastic range. In the straight silicone vessels, Zilver stents ($n = 2$)
 421 featuring a 7.0 mm diameter were deployed, and the final configuration was assessed qualitatively
 422 and quantitatively in terms of the final outer diameter (OD) of the vessel and compared against
 423 simulation results. In each patient-specific scenario, Zilver stents with a diameter of 6.0, 7.0 and 9.0
 424 mm were implanted. This allowed two clinical scenarios to be evaluated across three oversizing
 425 conditions, which represented the extreme cases of under-sizing and oversizing, as well as a condition
 426 of normal oversizing within the range⁴². The configurations of the deployed stents were acquired
 427 using 3D micro-CT scanning (μ CT-100, Scanco Medical, Switzerland) with an X-ray source of 70 kV and
 428 the Al filter of 0.5 mm. DICOM images from the micro-CT scans were compared against the cross-
 429 sectional images from the computational model through ImageJ software (National Institute of Health,
 430 USA) to quantify relevant clinical performance indicators, such as outer diameter (OD), minimum
 431 lumen area (MLA) and incomplete stent apposition (ISA) as illustrated **Figure 5c**.

432 4 Results

433 4.1 COU-1

434 4.1.1 COU-1 Calculation Verification in Radial Compression Simulation

435 4.1.1.1 Mesh Density (MD)

436 Global radial force and local maximum principal stresses of successive runs of the model with
437 increasing mesh density were quantified (**Figure 6**) and compared to the prediction obtained with the
438 8×8 grid (**Table 7**). For the global output, the coarsest mesh (3×3) showed the largest inaccuracy in
439 predicting the value of chronic outward force (*COF*) with a deviation of -13.8%, while the other grid
440 refinements predicted forces within $\pm 2\%$. As for the local output, mesh grids either over- or under-
441 predicted the maximum principal stress with a deviation below 2% when compared to the finest grid.
442 Overall, with mesh refinement, the element characteristic length decreased and the number of
443 elements in the grid increased, which contributed to larger computational times. An optimal
444 compromise was found for a 4×4 grid, which gave a reduction of 82% of CPU time and global and
445 local predictions with inaccuracy below 2%, comparable to the finest 8×8 mesh.

446

447 **Figure 6.** Calculation verification on mesh density for radial compression simulation: (a) radial force – diameter curves; (b)
 448 maximum principal stress – time curves; (c) contour plots of maximum principal stress for different mesh grids.

449 **Table 7.** Results of the calculation verification on mesh density applied to radial compression simulation.

Mesh Density	Verification			
	3 × 3	4 × 4	6 × 6	8 × 8
CPU Time	0.09C	0.20C	0.46C	C
Force at Maximum Crimp, N	0.63	0.59	0.59	0.58
Difference, %	8.94%	1.76%	1.54%	/
Chronic Outward Force, N	0.13	0.16	0.16	0.16
Difference, %	-13.83%	0.26%	-0.13%	/
Stress at Maximum Crimp, MPa	377.27	382.90	369.69	376.93
Difference, %	0.09%	1.58%	-1.92%	/

450

451 4.1.1.2 Element Integration (EI)

452 Global and local effects of different element integration options were assessed, with the results shown
 453 in **Figure 7**. The default option for reduced integration (Red-A) was considered as the reference model,
 454 as reduced integration is suggested in the Abaqus manual for hexahedral elements applied to bending
 455 problems (e.g., stent crimping and deployment)¹⁷. For the global output, the different *EI* options

456 resulted in an over-prediction of the force at maximum crimp in the range of +13.7% to +49.6% when
 457 compared to Red-A. Interestingly, lower discrepancies were found for the local output, where the
 458 over-prediction error was below +10%, except for the centroid option (Red-C) where a drop in
 459 maximum principal stress of -13.4% was reported. As for the computational time, reduced integration
 460 (Red-A, Red-O, Red-C) decreased the CPU time by 25% compared to full integration, however, the
 461 enhancement of hourglass control (Red-AH) increased the run time by 3-fold compared to default
 462 (Red-A).

463

464 **Figure 7.** Calculation verification on element integration applied to crimping simulation using a mesh density 4×4 : (a) radial
 465 force – diameter curves; (b) maximum principal stress – time curves; (c) contour plots of maximum principal stress.

466 **Table 8.** Results of the calculation verification on element integration applied to radial compression simulation.

Verification					
Element Integration	Full	Red-A	Red-AH	Red-O	Red-C
CPU Time	4.00C	C	3.20C	C	C
Force at Maximum Crimp, N	0.59	0.49	0.63	0.55	0.73
Difference, %	20.51%	/	29.25%	13.72%	49.60%
Chronic Outward Force, N	0.16	0.16	0.17	0.15	0.16

	Difference, %	0.00%	/	5.61%	-4.48%	1.92%
Stress at Maximum Crimp, MPa		382.90	352.95	356.70	358.11	305.77
	Difference, %	8.48%	/	1.06%	1.46%	-13.37%

467

468 **4.1.1.3 Target Time Increment (TTI)**

469 Global and local effects of different target time increments (*TTI*) were compared to the dynamic
470 implicit solver, which uses the implicit time integration to calculate the transient dynamic or quasi-
471 static response of a system, with results shown in **Figure 8** and **Table 9**. For the global output, the *TTI*
472 value had a minor influence on the radial force at maximum crimp, with a maximum variation of -
473 9.5%. Similarly, the local output only showed small discrepancies, with the largest deviation of -4.0%
474 compared to the dynamic implicit case. Overall, a *TTI* = 5.0E-06 s provided reliable results with
475 optimum performance in terms of computing time. For all the analyses, a peak of the KE to IE ratio
476 was found at the beginning of the simulation when the plates and the stent first come into contact
477 with one another, however, for the rest of the analyses this ratio was below 5% (**Figure 8c**), which is
478 the suggested criteria to ensure quasi-static conditions.

479

480 **Figure 8.** Calculation verification on target time increment applied to crimping simulation: (a) radial force – diameter
 481 curves; (b) maximum principal stress – time curves; (c) comparison of kinetic and internal energies in the TTI = 5.0E-06 s
 482 case; (d) comparison of kinetic to internal energy ratio trends.

483

Table 9. Results of the calculation verification activity on target time increment applied to crimping simulation.

Target Time Increment	Verification				
	Dyn Impl	1E-05 s	5E-06 s	1E-06 s	5E-07 s
CPU Time	20.53C	0.89C	0.89C	0.91C	C
Force at Maximum Crimp, N	0.64	0.58	0.59	0.59	0.59
Difference, %	/	-9.47%	-8.87%	-8.51%	-8.66%
Chronic Outward Force, N	/	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16
Difference, %	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Stress at Maximum Crimp, MPa	378.458	363.02	382.90	371.16	371.35
Difference, %	/	-4.08%	1.17%	-1.93%	-1.88%

484

485 **4.1.2 COU-1 Validation: Sensitivity Analysis on Model Inputs**

486 A sensitivity analysis of geometrical and material parameters of the Ni-Ti stent was carried out for the
 487 radial compression simulation (COU-1), whereby the effects on the global force and local stress
 488 parameters were quantified.

489 **4.1.2.1 Sensitivity Analysis of Stent Geometry**

490 The sensitivity analysis of strut thickness and width on global and local outputs is reported in **Figure 9**
 491 and **Table 10**. Greater effects were found for the radial force output, which consistently decreased or
 492 increased with respective decreases or increases in the strut dimensions. The variation of force at
 493 maximum crimp (-3.5% and +8.9%) and of chronic outward force (-0.9% and +16.1%) did not
 494 symmetrical decrease or increase with thickness. Reducing or increasing the width resulted in larger
 495 variations, both on the predicted force at maximum crimping (-22.2% and +24.9%) and of chronic
 496 outward force (-16.7% and +25.0%). Only minor effects on the maximum principal stress were found
 497 with the variation of the thickness (approx. 5.1%) and width (approx. 3.3%).

498 *Table 10. Comparison of model input sensitivity analysis on stent geometry.*

	Validation Model Inputs: Stent Geometry					
	Thickness (t_s)			Width (w_s)		
	$t_s - 10\%$	t_s	$t_s + 10\%$	$w_s - 10\%$	w_s	$w_s + 10\%$
Force at Maximum Crimp, N	0.59	0.61	0.66	0.47	0.61	0.76
Difference, %	-3.52%	/	+8.90%	-22.18%	/	+24.82%
Chronic Outward Force, N	0.16	0.16	0.18	0.13	0.16	0.20
Difference, %	-0.89%	/	16.10%	-16.64%	/	+24.99%
Stress at Maximum Crimp, MPa	383.98	366.98	387.30	379.79	366.98	378.09
Difference, %	+4.63%	/	+5.54%	3.49%	/	3.03%

499

500

501 **Figure 9.** Model input sensitivity analysis on stent geometry: (a) effects on the global QoI; (b) effects on the local QoI when
 502 strut thickness and width are varied.

503 4.1.2.2 Sensitivity Analysis of Nickel-Titanium Material Parameters

504 The sensitivity analysis of the Ni-Ti material parameters defined for the VUMAT superelastic behaviour
 505 ⁵³ on global and local QoIs is reported in **Figure 10** and **Table 11**. Comparing the radial force, the
 506 highest variations were caused by the austenitic elastic modulus E_A (-1.1% and +0.6%) and the start of
 507 transformation loading stress σ_L^S (-4.5% to +4.9%), primarily affecting the loading curve. The unloading
 508 portion of the curve was slightly affected by E_A , σ_L^S and σ_U^S (maximum difference of +2.9%, +11.0%, -
 509 7.1% respectively), while E_M , σ_L^E and σ_U^E had marginal effect on the whole radial force curve.

510 Concerning the distribution of stress at maximum crimping, the effects of a variation of E_A and E_M were
 511 below $\pm 1\%$. The highest effects were found for σ_L^S which recorded a deviation in the range of $\pm 9.5\%$
 512 while σ_L^E , σ_U^S and σ_U^E reported a variation below $\pm 1\%$.

513

514

515 **Figure 10.** Sensitivity analysis on Ni-Ti material parameters: (a) effects of each parameter on the radial force; (b) effects of
 516 each parameter on the maximum principal stress at a V-peak.

517 **Table 11.** Results for model inputs sensitivity analysis on nickel-titanium material parameters: values and errors reported
 518 for the radial force curve and the maximum principal stress at the maximum crimp configuration.

		Validation Model Inputs: Nickel-Titanium Parameters					
		Force at Maximum Crimp, N			Stress at Maximum Crimp, MPa		
		Ref. - 10%	Ref.	Ref.+ 10%	Ref. - 10%	Ref.	Ref.+ 10%
E_A	Value	0.58	0.59	0.59	366.96	365.24	363.45
	Difference, %	-1.05%	-	+0.61%	+0.47%	-	+0.00%
E_M	Value	0.58	0.59	0.59	364.99	365.24	363.45
	Difference, %	-0.74%	-	+0.61%	-0.07%	-	0.00%
σ_L^S	Value	0.56	0.59	0.62	330.53	365.24	398.00
	Difference, %	-4.52%	-	+4.86%	-9.50%	-	+9.51%
σ_L^E	Value	0.59	0.59	0.59	363.53	365.24	365.52
	Difference, %	-0.13%	-	+0.31%	-0.47%	-	+0.57%
σ_U^S	Value	0.59	0.59	0.59	364.96	365.24	364.96

	Difference, %	-0.13%	-	-0.13%	-0.08%	-	+0.42%
σ_u^E	Value	0.59	0.59	0.59	364.96	365.24	364.96
	Difference, %	-0.13%	-	-0.13%	-0.08%	-	+0.41%

519

520 4.2 COU-2

521 4.2.1 COU-2: Calculation Verification on Deployment Simulation

522 For COU-2, the impact of mesh density (*MD*), element integration (*EI*) and target time increment (*TTI*)
523 parameters on the predicted deployment configuration (e.g., inner lumen diameter, lumen gain) was
524 analysed. The nodal coordinates of the vessel pre- and post-implantation were analysed with
525 MATLAB® (v. 2021a, The Mathworks, Inc., Natick, MA) and the inner diameter was plotted against the
526 normalized length of the vessel in **Figure 11**. Additionally, the average inner diameter and the
527 corresponding lumen gain were computed and compared with the reference simulation in **Table 12**.

528 **Table 12.** Average inner diameter and lumen gain for different mesh density, element integration and target time
529 increment.

Verification on Deployment Simulation				
Mesh Density	3 × 3	4 × 4	6 × 6	8 × 8
Average Inner Diameter, mm	5.07	5.06	5.06	5.06
Difference, %	0.21%	0.02%	0.04%	-
Lumen Gain, mm	0.071	0.062	0.062	0.060
Difference, %	+17.53%	+1.95%	+3.01%	-
Element Integration	Full	Red-A	Red-O	Red-C
Average Inner Diameter, mm	5.06	5.06	5.06	5.05
Difference, %	-0.02%	-	0.00%	-0.17%
Lumen Gain, mm	0.062	0.063	0.063	0.054
Difference, %	-1.81%	-	+0.32%	-13.42%
Target Time Increment	1E-05 s	5E-06 s	1E-06 s	5E-07 s
Average Inner Diameter, mm	5.09	5.06	5.07	5.07
Difference, %	0.39%	-0.07%	0.02%	0.00%
Lumen Gain, mm	0.085	0.062	0.066	0.065
Difference, %	+30.54%	-5.71%	+1.35%	-

530

531 Generally, the parameters accounted for calculation verification did not provide relevant variations
532 for the prediction of the average inner diameter, with relative differences not larger than 2%. Greater
533 differences were found when considering the lumen gain, with substantial discrepancies arising when
534 3 × 3 mesh (+17.5%) and *TTI* = 1.0E-05 s (+30.5%) were considered.

535

536 **Figure 11.** Calculation verification on deployment simulation: effects on prediction of inner lumen diameter due to (a) mesh
 537 density, (b) element integration and (c) target time increment; (d) contact pressure generated in the vessel due to stent
 538 expansion.

539 4.2.2 COU-2: Validation with *In Vitro* Comparators

540 4.2.2.1 Deployment in a Silicone Straight Mock Vessel

541 The validation of the stent-vessel interaction was achieved by qualitative and quantitative comparison
 542 of the final deployment in a straight silicone vessel. In the experiments, the outer diameter (OD) of
 543 the vessel was 7.2 mm prior to deployment and reached an average 7.57 mm and 7.62 mm after stent
 544 implantation. The comparison of OD prediction from the *in silico* model along the stent axis was shown
 545 in **Figure 12a** and reported a maximum error of 1.0% (**Table 13**).

546

Table 13. Results of validation with straight mock vessel *in vitro* comparator.

Validation of Deployment: <i>in vitro</i> Straight Silicone Vessels	
Outer Diameter, mm [average ± SD]	Model Error, %

Experiment	Simulation	Maximum Error	Average Error
7.59 ± 0.06	7.60 ± 0.07	1.04%	0.40%

547
548
549

Figure 12. Validation of the deployment in the straight silicone mock vessel: **(a)** measurements of the outer diameter (OD); **(b)** qualitative comparison of the deployed configuration.

550 **4.2.2.2 Deployment in 3D-printed Patient-specific Vessels**

551 The comparison between *in silico* and *in vitro* deployment in patient-specific vessels A and B is
552 reported in **Figure 13** for all stent sizes. The *in silico* model successfully predicted the final
553 configurations both in a straighter geometry (A) and in curved/kinked geometry (B), capturing an
554 improved apposition of the stent to the inner lumen for increasing diameter size and correctly
555 identifying the locations along the vessel axis where strut-to-artery incomplete apposition occurred.

556

557 **Figure 13.** Validation of stent deployment in the 3D-printed patient-specific vessels: comparison of the deployment for
 558 different stent diameter sizes in scenarios A and B.

559 The quantitative comparison of the performance indicators is reported in **Figure 14**, where
 560 uncertainties arising from experiments were plotted as average and standard deviation over three
 561 measurements. The outer diameter (*OD*) was assessed in the proximal, central and distal portions of
 562 the vessel (*OD* was proposed as the metric for validation here as it could easily be measured by optical
 563 methods, should micro-CT not be available). The *in silico* model was successful in predicting the *OD*
 564 both for geometries A and B (**Figure 14a** and **b**) with an overall error smaller than +6.5%, although the
 565 level of accuracy depended on the local geometry and the vessel portion considered (**Table 14**). As for
 566 geometry A, the lowest accuracy was found in the distal region with the 9.0 mm device, while for B,
 567 the lowest accuracy was found in the central region with the 7.0 mm device (+5.0 %). The minimum
 568 lumen area (*MLA*) was evaluated by considering the minimum inner diameter along the vessel
 569 centreline. The *in silico* model predicted the *MLA* in the geometries A and B (**Figure 14c**) with the
 570 highest error of +17.4% for the 9.0 mm device in geometry A and +3.7% for the 7.0 mm device in
 571 geometry B.

572

Table 14. Measurement of the error among experimental and computational outcomes.

Stent Size	Validation of Deployment: <i>in vitro</i> Patient-specific Resin Vessels					
	Patient A			Patient B		
	6.0 × 60 mm	7.0 × 60 mm	9.0 × 60 mm	6.0 × 60 mm	7.0 × 60 mm	9.0 × 60 mm

Outer Diameter (OD)						
ϵ_{OD} -proximal, %	+2.07%	-1.02%	+1.92%	+3.18%	+1.05%	-2.67%
ϵ_{OD} -central, %	+4.68%	+0.01%	+6.35%	+1.70%	+4.99%	+0.42%
ϵ_{OD} -distal, %	-1.28%	-0.63%	+6.53%	-0.45%	+1.97%	+0.95%
Minimum Lumen Area (MLA)						
ϵ_{MLA} , %	+2.14%	-8.32%	+17.41%	+0.62%	+3.66%	-0.44%
Incomplete Stent Apposition (ISA)						
$ISA_{\mu CT}$, mm	0.34 (Y)	0.08 (N)	0.11 (N)	3.09 (Y)	0.96 (Y)	0.17 (N)
ISA_{FEA} , mm	0.37 (Y)	0.07 (N)	0.17 (N)	1.74 (Y)	0.96 (Y)	0.50 (Y)

573

574

575 **Figure 14.** Results of *in vitro* (black) and *in silico* (red) quantitative indicators: outer diameter measured in proximal,
576 central, and distal position for patient A (a) and B (b); minimal lumen area (c); incomplete stent apposition (d).

577 Incomplete stent apposition (ISA) was reported for the ring displaying the largest spacing from the

578 arterial wall, with comparisons between *in silico* models and *in vitro* comparators shown in **Figure 14**.

579 The model correctly predicted the location of the ring most detached from the wall, corresponding to

580 the 9th and 2nd rings in A and B respectively (black arrows in **Figure 13**). However, deviations on the
581 prediction of *ISA* magnitude were found, with the larger difference (-1.35 mm) reported for the 6.0
582 mm case in geometry B. Despite the deviation in the *ISA* value, the *in silico* model correctly predicted
583 the presence (Y) or absence (N) of malapposition (whose threshold is defined as the detachment
584 greater than strut thickness ⁷⁴) in all the cases, except for the 9.0 mm device in geometry B, where it
585 overestimated the detachment distance.

586 **4.3 COU-3**

587 **4.3.1 COU-3: Calculation Verification on Fatigue Behaviour Simulation**

588 The effects of mesh density (*MD*), element integration (*EI*) and target time increment (*TTI*) on
589 simulations of fatigue performance were assessed. The constant-life diagrams predicting the fatigue
590 life of the devices are depicted in **Figure 15**, while the mean strain (ϵ_m) and alternating strain (ϵ_a)
591 components, as well as the fatigue safety factor (*FSF*) are reported in **Table 15**. For the ϵ_m , value the
592 97.5th percentile was considered, as it gives a description of mean strain distribution and excludes
593 peak values that might arise due to artificial local concentration ⁴². Substantial differences were
594 observed due to mesh density, with the 3 × 3 and 6 × 6 grids under- and over-predicting the mean
595 strain distribution, with the 4 × 4 closer to the finer grid estimate. In the case of element integration,
596 it was found that Full and Red-C tended to over-estimate the mechanical response compared to the
597 default settings (Red-A). It was also found that as the *TTI* was decreased, the value of ϵ_m increased.

598 For the ϵ_a , the maximum value was considered and used in the evaluation of the fatigue safety factor
599 (*FSF*) as per Equation (3.4), which was then normalized with respect to the reference. While in all cases
600 the model is far from predicting failure, differences were found. Among the mesh grids, coarser
601 refinement tended to over-predict the fatigue life behaviour, with the *FSF* obtained from the 4 × 4 grid
602 being 6.5 times higher than the estimated *FSF* from the 8 × 8 grid. The choice of element integration
603 did not alter the prediction of fatigue behaviour greatly, except for the Red-O option, where the
604 prediction of *FSF* was approximately halved. The *TTI* substantially affected the *FSF*, with a 14.3-fold

605 increase for smaller *TTI*s, as opposed to the largest stable increment time. This was mainly due to the
 606 substantial effect that *TTI* had on the prediction of the alternating strain component.

607

608 **Figure 15.** Calculation verification applied to fatigue-life simulation accounting for the effects of mesh density, element
 609 integration and target time increment.

610 **Table 15.** Results of the calculation verification activities applied to fatigue analysis. The fatigue safety factor was
 611 normalized according to the reference case, here reported in the table with the symbol \bar{F} .

Verification COU-3											
<i>MD</i>	$\epsilon_m, \%$ 97.5 th	$\epsilon_a, \%$ max	<i>FSF</i> <i>norm.</i>	<i>EI</i>	$\epsilon_m, \%$ 97.5 th	$\epsilon_a, \%$ max	<i>FSF</i> <i>norm.</i>	<i>TTI</i>	$\epsilon_m, \%$ 97.5 th	$\epsilon_a, \%$ max	<i>FSF</i> <i>norm.</i>
3 × 3	0.71	0.008	2.51 \bar{F}	Full	0.95	0.003	1.22 \bar{F}	1E-05 s	0.88	0.012	0.07 \bar{F}
4 × 4	0.95	0.003	6.45 \bar{F}	Red-A	0.83	0.004	\bar{F}	5E-06 s	0.95	0.003	0.28 \bar{F}

6 × 6	1.05	0.016	1.25 \bar{F}	Red-O	0.81	0.008	0.45 \bar{F}	1E-06 s	1.01	0.003	0.32 \bar{F}
8 × 8	0.90	0.020	\bar{F}	Red-C	0.94	0.004	0.99 \bar{F}	5E-07 s	1.02	0.001	\bar{F}

612 5 Discussion

613 5.1 General

614 While finite element modelling is now widely used to support the design and testing phases of nickel-
615 titanium (Ni-Ti) cardiovascular devices ^{15,16,21,22}, there has been a lack of consensus on the
616 methodology to assess model credibility for decision-making ⁴⁴. The ASME VV-40 documentation ¹¹
617 provides a risk-informed credibility assessment of numerical models for medical devices by outlining
618 a general framework for verification and validation activities for numerical models. In this study, we
619 addressed relevant verification and validation activities for finite element modelling of self-expanding
620 Ni-Ti stents. Following a detailed literature review (Error! Reference source not found.), three different
621 contexts of use (COUs) were considered, namely (i) *Radial Compression* (ii) *Device Deployment* and (iii)
622 *Fatigue Life Estimates*, and several quantities of interest (QoIs) were addressed for each. Generally, it
623 was found that the chosen numerical parameters influenced global and local QoIs across all COUs
624 considered, although to varying levels of sensitivity. It was found that both global and local quantities
625 were highly sensitive to the mesh discretisation, with substantial variability in QoIs when the mesh
626 density was less than 4 × 4 elements across the strut cross-section, while the element formulation also
627 led to substantial variation depending on the chosen integration options. Furthermore, model results
628 were generally highly sensitive to the chosen target time increment, irrespective of whether the ratios
629 of kinetic and internal energies were kept below 5%. On the other hand, it was observed that model
630 results showed relatively low sensitivity to Ni-Ti material parameters, which suggests that the
631 calibration approaches used in the literature to date appear reasonable. While these general trends
632 were observed, it was found that the sensitivity of the model predictions greatly depended on the
633 COU being considered. Most notably, it was found that fatigue life estimates of Ni-Ti stents were
634 extremely sensitive to the selection of model parameters. It was concerning that the estimated fatigue

635 safety factor (*FSF*) could vary by almost an order of magnitude depending on the selection of model
636 parameters, with the target time increment (*TTI*) being one of the most influential parameters. In
637 contrast, the prediction of vessel diameter following deployment was least sensitive to numerical
638 parameters. Further detail and discussion on aspects of calculation verification and validation are
639 provided in Sections 5.2 and 5.3.

640 **5.2 Calculation Verification**

641 The temporal and spatial discretization of numerical models of Ni-Ti stents has not been extensively
642 investigated or reported in the literature, with only a limited number of studies considering such
643 details^{21,31,32}. In this study, a detailed investigation of calculation verification activity was conducted,
644 whereby the effects of mesh density (*MD*), element integration (*EI*) and mass scaling (*TTI*) were
645 addressed for each COU.

646 In terms of spatial discretization, it was found that element density and formulation had a significant
647 influence on the predictions of QoIs across each COU. It was found that an element density of 4×4
648 elements across the strut provided optimal results for both COU-1 and COU-2, since it gave a reduction
649 of up to 82% of computation time, while global and local QoIs were predicted within 2% of the solution
650 from the 8×8 grid. While this minimum density of 4×4 continuum elements has previously been
651 suggested^{17,19,29}, it was observed that the results for fatigue life estimate (COU-3) were more sensitive
652 to the choice of element size, with a 6.5-fold difference in *FSF* of the 4×4 elements compared to the
653 8×8 refinement. Together, these results indicate that at least 4×4 mesh across the strut width and
654 thickness should be used for the prediction of radial compression/deployment. In contrast, smaller
655 elements with at least 6×6 density or finer are suggested for fatigue life estimation, where a reliable
656 prediction of local strain and stress is necessary.

657 Considering element type, the analysis focused on linear hexahedral elements, which are widely used
658^{14-16,29}, and addressed full and reduced integration formulations. Within the reduced formulation,
659 three different options for the evaluation of the kinematic split (namely *average*, *orthogonal* and

660 *centroid*) were considered, and analyses were run with the 4 × 4-element grid. The use of the centroid
661 kinematic split (Red-C) resulted in the highest deviations in both COU-1 and COU-2, with +49.6%
662 deviation of force at maximum crimp (COU-1) and a deviation of -13.4% of lumen gain (COU-2),
663 compared to default reduced integration (Red-A). For COU-3, the difference was limited to Red-O
664 options which resulted in a 0.5-fold prediction of the *FSF*. Here, the default reduced integration option
665 (Red-A) is recommended as it provided the most appropriate predictions across all the COUs.
666 Additionally, the enhanced hourglass option, which has often been used in the literature^{31,52} to
667 counteract numerical artefacts, provided a better description of the radial behaviour, although it
668 resulted in a 3.2-fold rise in computational time when compared to default formulation.

669 In terms of temporal resolution, explicit solution schemes are most commonly used when modelling
670 Ni-Ti stents, with mass scaling approaches widely implemented to increase the required time
671 increment, enabling more efficient computation^{31,38}. With this approach, the most common
672 verification activity monitors the ratio of kinetic and internal energies to ensure that these are below
673 5%⁷⁵. In this study, a systematic investigation of the target time increment (*TTI*) selected during the
674 mass scaling procedure was carried out on the 4 × 4-element grid, with model results across all COUs
675 generally being highly sensitive to this parameter. It was found that *TTI* had a substantial impact on
676 the prediction of lumen gain in the deployment simulation (COU-2), with up to 30% difference
677 between *TTI* = 1.0E-05 s and smaller values. Furthermore, the stable time increment with *TTI* = 1.0E-5
678 s under-predicted the *FSF* (COU-3) by over ten-fold compared to the smaller *TTI*. On the other hand,
679 smaller deviations were found for radial behaviour (COU-1) with the larger *TTI* being within 10% of the
680 reference value from a dynamic implicit solution when predictions of global radial force and local
681 prediction of stress at maximum crimping were considered. Importantly, this study demonstrated that
682 substantial deviations in predicted QoIs were observed across different models, even though the
683 ratios of kinetic to internal energies were well below 5% for most of the analysis. This implies that a
684 careful sensitivity analysis for *TTI* is required, irrespective of whether the ratios of kinetic and internal
685 energies are below 5%. It is also important to note that the *TTIs* used here are only relevant to the

686 specific model parameters also selected here and *TTIs* are not broadly applicable to other models. The
687 appropriate selection of mass scaling parameters and *TTIs* is uniquely dependent on the specific
688 parameters of an individual model (e.g., step time, element size, loading amplitudes etc).

689 **5.3 Validation Activities**

690 **5.3.1 Model Input Sensitivity**

691 Validation of the model inputs was carried out to determine the sensitivity of the model to stent
692 geometry and nickel-titanium material parameters for COU-1 and COU-2. The rationale behind this
693 activity was motivated by the fact that model geometries and material-level parameters for nickel-
694 titanium devices are not always widely available ⁷⁶.

695 Considering the geometric features, the dimensions of Ni-Ti stents are often acquired with different
696 imaging techniques ^{14,15,19,29,65}, which are subject to some degree of uncertainty during measurements.
697 Even when the geometry is known (e.g., CAD is provided by the stent manufacturer), it typically
698 represents the laser-cut configuration that could be altered during further manufacturing processes.
699 For instance, electropolishing can result in differences in overall final outer diameters ⁷⁷, with removal
700 up to 21 μm possible during this step ⁷⁸. Our results showed that a 10% variation in stent thickness
701 altered the prediction of the radial *COF* by up to 16.1%, while it altered the predicted maximum stress
702 by only 5.5%. On the other hand, variation of the strut width had a greater influence on predicted
703 quantities, with deviations up to 25.0% for *COF* while the deviation on the prediction of the maximum
704 stress were in line (+3.5%). Even though the influence of geometric dimensions is largely consistent
705 with their relative contribution to the second moment of area, these results do indicate that the
706 correct geometry is required to correctly predict global responses.

707 In terms of the Ni-Ti parameters, material-level data of devices is rarely available, and some studies
708 have been forced to calibrate the material parameters to the radial response of the device ^{13,45,79}, with
709 certain challenges in this activity given the large number of parameters to be determined. It was
710 generally found in this study that model predictions were not overly sensitive to the nickel-titanium

711 parameter description. For the conditions analysed, only a few parameters, namely E_A and σ_L^S , had an
712 influence on the predicted global and local QoIs, although the differences were not larger than 4.9%
713 in force and 9.5% in stress. These results indicate a certain amount of sensitivity to material inputs,
714 where the behaviour of different regions of the radial force curve depends on specific material
715 parameters. Although, this analysis shows that a calibration approach based on radial compression
716 tests appears suitable to tune the main parameters that influence the device behaviour in crimping
717 and deployment. Nevertheless, when considering more extreme deformation, other parameters such
718 as the martensite modulus E_M , the stress at the start of unloading σ_L^S , or the maximum transformation
719 strain in tension ε_L might require an appropriate calibration through a different mechanical test.

720 **5.3.2 *In vitro* Comparison of Stent Deployment into Mock Vessels**

721 Several computational models have been employed to predict the deployment of Ni-Ti devices,
722 however, only a limited number of studies have considered *in vitro* approaches for the validation of
723 this simulation^{21,22}. For peripheral stents, whose main function is to restore patency by expanding the
724 inner lumen of the vessel, deployment simulations have been used to predict parameters such as the
725 lumen gain^{16,38,48}, though an analysis of the accuracy of such predictions has not been reported. Recently,
726 a quantitative validation approach was proposed for balloon-expandable coronary stents by Berti et
727 al.⁴³, who measured the outer diameter post-deployment in a mock vessel comparator. In our study,
728 we have employed a similar strategy whereby the predicted deployment configuration was directly
729 compared to straight and 3D-printed mock vessel comparators. For the patient-specific vessels,
730 several testing conditions were taken into consideration, which included different geometries and
731 different stent nominal diameter sizes, thereby increasing the credibility of the model since each
732 scenario represented an independent validation point⁸. Each material for the mock vessel, namely
733 silicone for the straight vessel and 3D-printed resin for patient-specific geometry was characterised
734 through tensile tests either on a sample cut from the vessel (silicone) or from dog-bone specimens
735 that were 3D-printed with the same settings as the vessels (e.g., printing angle, curing temperature

736 and time). Furthermore, the numerical model parameters of these simulations were those identified
737 to be optimal based on the previous verification activities.

738 Straight vessel scenario showed that measurements taken on *in vitro* comparators have inherent
739 relative uncertainty of approx. 0.8%. Based on this, it was found that the predicted deployment in
740 straight silicone mock vessel closely agreed with the *in vitro* comparators, with the prediction of outer
741 diameter (*OD*) following deployment resulting in an average error of only 1.04%.

742 Deployment into patient-specific 3D-printed vessels was used to assess *OD* prediction, as previously
743 performed ⁴³, as well as minimum lumen area (*MLA*) and incomplete stent apposition (*ISA*) ⁴², which
744 are highly relevant from a clinical point of view. Again, it was found that the measurement of *OD* was
745 generally accurate across all mock vessels, irrespective of the acquisition method (measurement from
746 optical images vs. measurements on cross-sectional images acquired with micro-CT), with only an
747 average error of 1.65% across the scenarios (A and B) and the different stent sizes considered. It was
748 also found that the model could accurately predict the *MLA*, with only an average error of 2.08%. In
749 predicting malapposition to the vessel wall, it was determined that the model could correctly predict
750 the locations in which *ISA* occurred across all models. Although, the precise magnitude of the *ISA* had
751 an average error of 33.7%, with these errors likely arising due to uncertainties related to stent
752 positioning in the vessel (e.g., use of centreline vs. guidewire for the *in silico* deployment) and the very
753 small resolution of these measurements. These results suggest that in the context of patient-specific
754 predictions of stent deployment, a model validated with *in vitro* idealised (i.e., cylindrical, and straight)
755 vessels will provide an accurate prediction of lumen gain and lumen area. However, the prediction of
756 local deployment features, such as malapposition, is more challenging and requires sophisticated
757 models and experimental comparators to ensure credibility.

758 **5.4 Limitations**

759 Among the limitations of the study, the following aspects are worth consideration. A reduced unit of
760 the stent (and vessel) and axisymmetric boundary conditions around the circumferential axis were

761 applied for calculation verification and sensitivity analysis. Despite being a simplification of the more
762 complex response of a full stent, the radial behaviour appropriately scaled (e.g., radial force
763 normalization) was deemed to be representative of experimental outcomes while providing efficient
764 computational times. In the calculation verification, predictions could not be evaluated against a
765 closed-form analytical solution so, instead, the QoIs from an explicit solution scheme was compared
766 to the more highly resolved versions of an implicit analysis. While this provides an indication of QoIs
767 converging towards a solution (where error becomes progressively minimised) for both stable time
768 increment and mesh density, the analysis around element type does not yield a converged solution
769 but instead shows differences in predictions for different element formulations. Also, for verification
770 activities, the results hereby presented were obtained with Abaqus, which could provide different
771 outcomes when different software is chosen. While the methodology is applicable to different stent
772 designs, the results here reported (e.g., sensitivity analysis on model inputs) are representative of the
773 specific device accounted.

774 **6 Conclusion and Recommendations**

775 This work focused on a self-expanding nickel-titanium stent and developed a finite element model to
776 address the credibility steps required for contexts of use (COUs) commonly reported in the literature,
777 namely radial compression test (COU-1), stent deployment in a vessel (COU-2) and fatigue life
778 predictions (COU-3). As per the VV-40 standard ¹¹, a series of verification and validation activities were
779 performed, and their relevance was assessed over the COUs and their quantities of interests (QoIs)
780 and several recommendations are have been made.

781 In terms of calculation verification, it is recommended to:

- 782 ▪ Use at least 4×4 element density across the strut width and thickness for prediction of radial
783 compression/deployment; while a 6×6 element density or finer are more appropriate for
784 fatigue life estimation where a reliable prediction strain/stress is necessary.
- 785 ▪ Conduct a careful sensitivity analysis on the effects of mass scaling options on the QoIs,
786 irrespective of whether the ratios of kinetic and internal energies are below 5%.

787 ▪ Use reduced integration over full integration continuum hexahedral elements to avoid overly
788 stiff behaviour in bending, with enhanced hourglass control options providing additional
789 benefits, although at increased computational cost.

790 Considering model inputs and model validation,

791 ▪ The sensitivity analysis on geometrical and material inputs highlighted the importance of
792 correctly capturing the geometric dimensions of the stent, in particular the strut width, while
793 model results were less sensitive to Ni-Ti material parameters, suggesting that device-level
794 calibration of material behaviour are reasonable.

795 ▪ The validation of stent deployment through the use of idealised vessel geometries offers a
796 simple and accurate validation method when predicting lumen gain, and lumen area, provided
797 that the material of the vessel is appropriately characterized and modelled. However,
798 predictions of local stent-to-lumen interactions require more sophisticated validation
799 approaches.

800

7 Appendix

Table A 1. Literature review of structural analysis of self-expanding nickel-titanium devices for endovascular applications (n/a = not available).

Reference	Device, FE Model Description and Solver	Input and Output Data	Verification and Validation Activities
Gökgöl et al. (2015) ¹⁶	<p>Device: Astron-Pulsar and Astron (Biotronik, Switzerland) for peripheral applications.</p> <p>FE Model: large and complex interactions among components caused discontinuities.</p> <p>Solver: Explicit (Abaqus, Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp., USA).</p>	<p>Input Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Geometry: reconstruction methodology not described. ▪ Material: superelastic behaviour of Nickel-titanium, with parameters provided by the stent manufacturer. ▪ Mesh Density: density n/a; total number of elements of 173,160 and 91,248 for the two devices respectively. ▪ Element Type: linear brick element with reduced integration (C3D8R). ▪ Target Time Increment: 4.0E-06 s. <p>Output Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Radial force curve for mechanical comparison. ▪ Lumen gain and arterial stress after implantation. ▪ Strain distribution in the stent for fatigue analysis. 	<p>Verification:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stent mesh density assessed with a sensitivity analysis that monitored the maximum principal strain until changes less than 2.5% was found. ▪ Target time increment ensured that ratio of kinetic to internal energy was below 5% (quasi-static condition). <p>Validation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Artery axial and circumferential behaviour assessed through comparison with published experimental data from uniaxial extension. ▪ Stent mechanical behaviour was compared with radial force data from experiments.
Conti et al. (2017) ¹⁵	<p>Device: PRECISE Stent (Cordis Endovascular, Florida USA) for peripheral applications.</p> <p>FE Model: Nonlinear, large deformation, complex contact (general contact algorithm).</p> <p>Solver: Explicit (Abaqus, Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp., USA)</p>	<p>Input Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Geometry: high resolution micro-CT scan of a real sample. ▪ Material: superelastic VUMAT (Auricchio & Taylor ⁵³), with material parameter derived from literature. ▪ Mesh Density: density n/a; total number of element (421,872) and nodes (787,500). ▪ Element Formulation: linear brick element with reduced integration (C3D8R). ▪ Target Time Increment: n/a. <p>Output Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stent configuration and Von Mises stress distribution for straight and bent leg positions. 	<p>Verification: n/a.</p> <p>Validation: n/a.</p>

<p>Allegretti et al. (2018) ¹⁴</p>	<p>Device: Two stents featuring a peak-to-valley and a peak-to-peak design for peripheral applications. FE Model: n/a. Solver: ANSYS Mechanical APDL 17.2 (Ansys, Inc.).</p>	<p>Input Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Geometry: CAD reconstruction based on measurements from optical analyses. A sub-unit of the stent was modelled (3 and 4 rings for the two devices respectively). ▪ Material: superelastic material formulation available in the commercial solver; material parameters derived from axial tensile tests on three-wires dog-bone specimens. ▪ Mesh Density: number of elements of 197,000 and 203,000 for the two devices respectively. ▪ Element Formulation: 3D 8-node structural solid element with simplified enhanced formulation. ▪ Target Time Increment: n/a. <p>Output Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Force-displacement curves from axial tensile tests. ▪ Mean and alternating strain in the stent for fatigue life assessment under cyclic loading conditions. 	<p>Verification:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stent mesh density assessed with a sensitivity analysis that monitored the stress and strain at the maximal loaded points of the structures and global reaction forces. <p>Validation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Material parameters were extracted from the experimental tensile tests on dog-bone specimen then compared with a FE model of the dog-bone traction. ▪ Stent model validated with a comparison of simulation and experimental results of axial/compression tests on the devices ▪ Comparison of most critical zone in the stent structure in the simulation and in the experiments under fatigue cycle loading.
<p>Lei et al. (2019) ¹⁹</p>	<p>Device: E-Luminexx ZVL08060 stent (Bard, USA) for peripheral stenting. FE Model: high nonlinearity due to material, geometry and complex displacement-driven contact problem (surface-to-surface contact pair). Solver: Explicit (Abaqus, Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp., USA).</p>	<p>Input Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Geometry: CAD reconstruction based on measurement from high resolution micro-CT scan of a real sample. ▪ Material: superelastic VUMAT (Auricchio & Taylor ⁵³), with material parameter derived from literature on a different stent design. ▪ Mesh Density: 4 × 4 element density in width and thickness. ▪ Element Formulation: incompatible linear brick elements (C3D8I). ▪ Target Time Increment: n/a. <p>Output Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Contour plot of radial displacement in deployment simulation in the stent and the artery. ▪ Mean and alternating strain in the stent for fatigue analysis under physiological biomechanical conditions. 	<p>Verification:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mesh density sensitivity analysis mentioned but details are not reported. ▪ Selection of appropriate loading rate to ensure the simulation to be quasi-static. Evaluation based on the extraction of fundamental frequencies of stent and artery; addition of damping for energy-absorption. <p>Validation: n/a.</p>

<p>Feng et al. (2019) ²⁰</p>	<p>Device: Innovative stents designed for iliac vein patented by the authors. FE Model: larges scale deformation, nonlinear problem. The generalized variational principle and the penalty function method were used. Solver: Explicit (Abaqus, Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp., USA)</p>	<p>Input Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Geometry: designed and developed by the authors. ▪ Material: perfectly elastic material fitted to uniaxial tensile test of the Nickel-titanium tube specimen; material parameters n/a. ▪ Mesh Density: n/a ▪ Element Formulation: n/a. ▪ Target Time Increment: n/a. <p>Output Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Maximum principal strain distribution in stent during radial compression. ▪ Maximum principal strain distribution in stent and Von Mises stress distribution in artery after implantation. ▪ Mean and alternating strain for fatigue analysis 	<p>Verification: n/a Validation: n/a</p>
<p>Shen et al. (2020) ³⁵</p>	<p>Device: Prototype with a tapered designed, application n/a (outer proximal diameter of 1.74 mm). FE Model: n/a. Solver: n/a (Abaqus, Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp., USA).</p>	<p>Input Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Geometry: designed by the authors. ▪ Material: superelastic VUMAT (Auricchio & Taylor ⁵³), with material parameters derived from literature. ▪ Mesh Density: 92'945-105'401 elements. ▪ Element Formulation: quadratic tetrahedral elements (C3D10). ▪ Target Time Increment: n/a. <p>Output Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Von Mises stress distribution in the stent and reaction moment in bending deformation. 	<p>Verification:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mesh density sensitivity analysis mentioned but details are not reported. <p>Validation: n/a.</p>
<p>Hung et al. (2021) ³⁶</p>	<p>Device: prototype for thrombectomy with a V-shaped design, closed cells and irregular spikes to engage with the blood clot. FE Model: n/a. Solver: Implicit (Abaqus, Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp., USA).</p>	<p>Input Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Geometry: designed by the authors. ▪ Material: superelastic UMAT (Auricchio & Taylor ⁵³), with material parameters derived from literature. ▪ Element Formulation: not specified for the stent, the blood clot is meshed with incompatible linear brick elements (C3D8I). ▪ Target Time Increment: n/a (implicit was used). <p>Output Data:</p>	<p>Verification: n/a. Validation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>In vitro</i> experiments addressed, but not compared with the FEA (e.g., <i>in vitro</i> test to remove the blood clot are performed but not compared with a simulation).

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Geometric configuration and plastic strain in the device in the expanded, welded, and crimped configurations. 	
<p>Zaccaria et al. (2021) ²¹</p>	<p>Device: ID Branch and ID Cav (ID NEST MEDICAL, Strasbourg, France) for the treatment of May-Thurner syndrome in leg veins.</p> <p>FE Model: Nonlinear model, large deformation, complex interaction (general contact algorithm).</p> <p>Solver: Explicit (Abaqus, Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp., USA).</p>	<p>Input Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Geometry: ID Branch was built using 3D parametric equations, with geometrical parameters evaluated from pictures of the stent in the extended configuration; the ID Cav geometry was built from the drawing for the laser-cut procedure. ▪ Material: material parameters were calibrated based on tensile tests performed on wire specimen provided by the manufacturer. ▪ Mesh Density: 5'548 elements (ID Branch) and 9'243 elements (ID Cav). ▪ Element Formulation: linear beam formulation (B31). ▪ Target Time Increment: n/a. <p>Output Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Force-displacement curve in radial compression test, tensile test and free release test. ▪ Von Mises stresses the assembled devices. ▪ Device configuration, von Mises stress in the device, maximum principal stress and strain fields, and contact pressure in the artery when deployed in a realistic geometry. 	<p>Verification:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mesh refinements (coarse, medium and fine) and element type (linear brick elements with reduced integration C3D8R, beam elements B31) assessed on a single unit (V strut). The comparison took included outputs such as reaction force, Von Mises stress and computational time reported as % error w.r.t. the brick element finer mesh. ▪ Material parameters were calibrated from tensile tests at 25°C and 37°C on wire samples, multi-wire specimens, laser-cut stent struct, compared with FEA on a single cube and the multi-wire specimen. ▪ Friction coefficient effects evaluated on the force-diameter curve. ▪ Butterworth filter was applied to both the experimental and numerical curves to reduce the oscillations caused by the explicit method. <p>Validation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Device models were validated with radial compression or axial tests by comparing in silico outcomes with experiments ($n = 3$ to ensure the test repeatability). The comparison accounted for force-displacement curve (quantitative) and deformation (qualitatively). Different tests were conceived for the different components (either radial compression or tensile test). The assembled device was tested with axial extraction. ▪ Release and recapture procedure was validated in terms of force-displacement curves from pushing/pulling the hub of the delivery system. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Deployment in a realistic geometry validated in terms device configuration (qualitative).
<p>Hejazi et al. (2021) ⁸⁰</p>	<p>Device: Diamond design, Chevron design, Z-design and braided design for the</p>	<p>Input Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Geometry: n/a. 	<p>Verification:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Characteristic element length based on a mesh sensitivity analysis (details not reported).

	<p>treatment of venous obstruction. FE Model: n/a. Solver: Implicit (Abaqus, Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp., USA).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Material: superelastic UMAT based on Auricchio & Taylor⁵³, Bhattacharya, Lagoudas model⁸¹, with material parameter derived from literature. ▪ Mesh Density: elements with characteristic length varying from 0.075 mm to 0.05 mm. ▪ Element Formulation: quadratic brick element with full integration (C3D20). ▪ Target Time Increment: n/a (implicit was used). <p>Output Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Von Mises stress distribution in the device. ▪ Bending force-circumferential displacement curves. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Radial pressure calculated based on an analytical equation was compared with data points corresponding to <i>in vitro</i> experiment. <p>Validation: n/a.</p>
<p>McKenna et al. (2021)²⁹</p>	<p>Device: Precise Pro (Cordis Endovascular, Johnson & Johnson, USA) self-expanding laser-cut stent with and without polymer covering for biliary or femoropopliteal stenting. Additional stent designs and stiffer polymer covers were considered. FE Model: nonlinear model, large deformation, complex interaction (general contact algorithm), penalty contact method (friction coefficient $\nu = 0.2$). Solver: Explicit (Abaqus, Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp., USA).</p>	<p>Input Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Geometry: reconstructed from analysing microscope images with ImageJ image processing software. The repeating unit was drawn, meshed, patterned, and wrapped to create the stent cylindrical geometry. ▪ Material: superelastic VUMAT (Auricchio & Taylor⁵³), with material parameter calibrated over radial force and axial compression tests for the stent; elastic plastic constitutive behaviour for the cover (PU-PTFE), whose parameters were derived from uniaxial tests on a strip of the sample. ▪ Mesh Density: 4 × 5 in width and thickness, for a total of approx. 470,000 elements. ▪ Element Formulation: linear brick element with reduced integration (C3D8R) and enhanced hourglass control. ▪ Target Time Increment: n/a, such that the ratio of kinetic energy to internal energy is kept below 5% after initial contact between the stent and rigid surfaces. <p>Output Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Force - displacement curve in radial compression and axial compression tests. ▪ Bending configuration (qualitatively). 	<p>Verification n/a. Validation: radial compression, axial compression and bending tests, used to calibrate Nickel-titanium parameters.</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Max principal stress distribution in the stent and in the polymeric cover. 	
<p>Luraghi et al. (2021) ²²</p>	<p>Device: EmboTrap II (CERENOVUS, Galway, Ireland) for trapping and removing blood clot in case of acute ischaemic stroke in brain arteries.</p> <p>FE Model: self-penalty hard contact.</p> <p>Solver: Explicit (LS-DYNA Release 11.0, ANSYS, Canonsburg, PA, USA).</p>	<p>Input Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geometry: CAD model was analysed to extract centreline of the frame and built the wire model, which was assigned a rectangular cross-section. The cross-section dimensions were measured with a confocal laser scanning microscope. Material: shape memory material constitutive formulation available in the commercial finite-element solver. The Nickel-titanium material parameters, provided by the manufacturer. Mesh Density: characteristic length of 0.2 mm, total amount of elements of 4,353. Element Formulation: Hughes-Liu beam elements with a rectangular cross section. Target Time Increment: n/a, mass scaling (time step = 5E-07 s) and mass proportional damping factor (10 s^{-1}) selected such that the ratio of kinetic energy to internal energy is kept below 2%. <p>Output Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Force-displacement curve of axial tensile tests on the device. Configuration of crimping procedure (qualitative). Thrombectomy procedure in a U-bend tube, funnel-shaped tube, and patient-specific silicone tube. Von Mises stress and strain in the blood clot during thrombectomy procedure. 	<p>Verification:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mesh density was assessed with three different grids (average element size of 0.4 mm, 0.2 mm and 0.1 mm). Resultant force and the axial stresses on selected elements in the central part of the device used as monitored variables for the convergence analysis. <p>The authors published more recently a verification study where mesh density, element formulation and integration were comprehensively addressed ³¹.</p> <p>Validation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Material parameters with axial tensile test on the device level (quantitative). Thrombectomy procedure in a U-bend tube, funnel-shape tube, patient-specific silicone tube (qualitative). Silicone tube was used for the <i>in vitro</i> comparator, in the FE model the vessels were modelled as rigid bodies.
<p>He et al. (2022) ³⁸</p>	<p>Device: Zilver (Cook, USA), and modified/personalised design.</p> <p>FE Model: contact pair interaction between the stent and the vessel, general hard contact with a friction coefficient $\nu = 0.2$.</p>	<p>Input Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geometry: not reported for the Zilver, other designs were built by the authors. Plaque model was constructed with from DICOM images of a patient's femoropopliteal plaque using CT imaging. Material: superelastic VUMAT (Auricchio and Taylor ⁵³) with material parameter from literature (different stent design). 	<p>Verification:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mesh density and element type selected according to previous studies of the same authors ^{63,82}. Schiavone et al. (2016) ⁶³ selected a 4×4 mesh density of linear brick elements with full integration and incompatible mode (C3D8I) considering the numerical convergence in terms diameter change, recoiling and stress distribution (data not reported). Qui et al. (2018) ⁸² selected a 5×6 mesh density

	<p>Solver: Explicit (Abaqus, Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp., USA).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mesh Density: 4 × 4 in width and thickness. ▪ Element Formulation: linear brick elements with reduced integration (C3D8R). ▪ Target Time Increment: 1E-08 s, obtained by selecting a mass scaling factor of 1000, damping coefficient of 1.2 for quadratic bulk viscosity. <p>Output Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lumen gain and cross-section shape post deployment. ▪ Von Mises stress in the artery (media layer). 	<p>of linear brick elements with reduced integration (C3D8R). Noticeably, the mesh density relies on different stent geometries and materials: Xience (Abbott, USA) stent in Co–Cr alloy L605⁶³ and Absorb (Abbott, USA) stent in polymeric material (PLLA)⁸².</p> <p>Validation: n/a.</p>
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1 Declaration of Competing Interest

2 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships
3 that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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